

PHARMACOEPIDEMOLOGY CHARACTERISTICS OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA IN FERGANA VALLEY REGION (BASED ON THE RESULTS OF 20 YEARS OF MONITORING)

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The purpose of the study is to identify and evaluate modern pharmacoepidemiological characteristics of bronchial asthma (BA) in the Fergana Valley region.

Research material and methods. In 2001-2021, pharmacoepidemiological monitoring was organized in the conditions of Andijan. 1663 patients (594 men and 1069 women aged $\geq 18-90$ years) with BA treated at RRCEM AB were taken as subjects.

BA was diagnosed and monitored using GINA (2011) criteria, pharmacotherapy alternatives were determined and assessed using a special pharmacoepidemiological questionnaire.

Results and conclusions. Mainly, the adult population uses drugs that are based and recommended for use at the international level. They make up 99% of all preparations. 4 types of ICS (beclazone ECO, budesonide, fluticasone or flixotide) and nebulizer therapy are used purposefully and purposefully. The use of inhaled glucocorticosteroids increased by 2.1%, the use of anti-leukotriene drugs decreased by 6.9%, the prescription of short-acting $\beta 2$ agonists decreased by 1.2%, and the targeted use of basic anti-inflammatory drugs decreased by 0.9%.

In contrast, the use of drugs other than inhaled glucocorticosteroids has increased over the past 20 years: long-acting $\beta 2$ agonists (by 4.0%), inhaled anticholinergics (by 7.5%), short-acting theophyllines (by 10.5%), and combined antiasthmatic drugs (by 6.3%). Methylprednisolone, systemic glucocorticosteroids, mucolytics, magnesium sulfate and antihistamines of the 2nd and 3rd generations were used as "auxiliary antiasthmatic drugs".

These data are of medical-economical and preventive importance.

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